

The Soviet Family on the Stage of Change: Digital Approaches to Ideology and Childhood in Postwar Children's Drama

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The concept of the family has long played a foundational role in global culture, but in Soviet ideology it took on a particularly significant and politicized function. Central to this was the myth of the “Great Family” (Clark, 2000), an ideological construct in which the socialist state was imagined as an extension of the nuclear family. Soviet citizens were cast as the “sons” of a benevolent “father,” embodied in the figure of Joseph Stalin. Yet this raises several questions: Did this myth fully supplant representations of the “small” or nuclear family? What familial structures and ideals were promoted? What kind of child was idealized in Soviet culture? And how did these ideals change after Stalin’s death?

My PhD dissertation explores these questions by applying digital humanities methods to a corpus of Soviet children’s plays. The project examines the ideological construction of the family in postwar Soviet culture by analyzing how family models were represented on stage during late Stalinism (1945–1953) and the Thaw (1954–1964). Children’s theatre is a particularly revealing object for such an inquiry: it functioned as one of the most effective instruments of Soviet propaganda, shaping behavioral norms and ideological responses for the youngest “comrades” (Dobrenko, 2011). The children’s stage was often deeply polarized—presenting a clear divide between good and bad, right and wrong, us and them—making it a rich site for the analysis of state ideology.

With the weakening of censorship after Stalin’s death, theatrical representations of family and childhood began to shift. As Catriona Kelly notes, the process of de-Stalinization was complex and uneven, difficult to trace through traditional close reading alone (Kelly, 2007). To meet this challenge, I adopt a hybrid approach that combines qualitative and quantitative methods, following the broader intellectual lineage of distant reading (Moretti, 2013) and computational literary analysis (Jockers, 2013; Underwood, 2019). Using digital tools, I trace thematic and linguistic change across a corpus of 54 Soviet children’s plays. All plays were digitized, transcribed, and marked up according to TEI principles (cf. Burnard, 2014; Ide & Véronis, 1995;

Romary, 2008; Sperberg-McQueen & Burnard, 1995). The corpus is based on scans from two leading Soviet theatrical journals — *Teatr* and *Pionerskii teatr*. Full-text plays are not publicly available because they remain under copyright (Russian copyright law protects works for the author’s lifetime plus 70 years). However, aggregated data, metadata, and analytical code may be shared upon request.

Before analysis, the corpus underwent a standardized preprocessing workflow including OCR correction, lemmatization, and the removal of stage directions and character names. The final dataset consists of two subcorpora: 23 Stalinist plays (141,264 tokens) and 31 Thaw plays (161,900 tokens), with vocabulary sizes and token counts calculated after lemmatization to ensure comparability.

My analysis focuses on how the image of the family was constructed and transformed in these two periods. Following the framework developed by Evgeny Dobrenko (2020), I interpret family representations in light of the interrelation between cultural policy and political ideology. The digital component of the project relies on three principal techniques:

1. TF-IDF (Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency).

I calculated the top 100 TF-IDF–weighted words in each subcorpus. This method, widely used in information retrieval (Manning, Raghavan & Schütze, 2008; Salton & Buckley, 1988), highlights words that are especially characteristic of individual texts relative to the corpus. These results illuminate the prominence of family vs. collective vocabulary, and emotional vs. ideological registers.

2. Z-Analysis.

To complement TF-IDF, I applied Z-score analysis, commonly used in corpus linguistics for inter-corpus comparison (Evert, 2008). Whereas TF-IDF captures internal distinctiveness, Z-scores identify significant differences in lexical distributions across the two periods. This allows for tracing shifts in ideological emphasis between Stalinism and the Thaw.

3. Topic Modeling (LDA and STM).

Using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (Blei, Ng & Jordan, 2003; Blei, 2012), I extracted four stable thematic clusters across the corpus: leisure, patriotism, coming of age, and struggle against enemies. Structural Topic Modeling (Roberts et al., 2014; Roberts et al., 2019) enabled me to incorporate temporal metadata and visualize how thematic prominence changed over time.

Topic interpretation was triangulated with close reading, concordance analysis in AntConc, and extensive reference to scholarship on Soviet culture and literary ideology. This methodological blending supports a more nuanced account of the cultural shifts at stake, demonstrating how quantitative tools can reveal patterns otherwise difficult to detect.

By combining computational methods with traditional cultural analysis, this project shows how children’s theatre—an understudied but ideologically charged genre—offers a valuable lens for understanding the evolution of Soviet family ideology. The research also contributes to broader discussions in digital humanities on how distant

reading can illuminate political aesthetics, narrative structures, and cultural memory.

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